

Enabling Lightweight Federated Learning in NextG Wireless Networks

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Abstract—NextG wireless will heavily rely on Federated Learning (FL) applications to learn context-aware AI solutions from the massive amount of generated data. Ensuring the reliability of wireless links for such applications is paramount, especially for FL where packet loss can severely hamper performance and efficiency. Traditional approaches fall short under the high packet loss characteristics of wireless networks. This demo shows how the integration of Fountain Codes (FC) into the FL process can bring notable improvements in packet transmission efficiency, especially under high packet loss conditions.

Index Terms—Fountain Codes, Federated Learning, Wireless Networks, Radio Access Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Next Generation (NextG) wireless networks are envisioned to fundamentally transform the architectural paradigms of current network infrastructures. This transformation is expected to impose a shift towards a communication infrastructure characterized by fully decentralized control mechanisms alongside the virtualization of network resources, as detailed in [1]. Within this architectural perspective, the role of distributed Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies is expected to be of paramount importance. Indeed, the integration of distributed AI is considered critical for effectively managing the large amount of data generated across the network and for realizing network intelligence [2].

In particular, Federated Learning (FL) [3], [4] can enable devices to collaboratively learn a globally shared Machine Learning (ML) model among User Equipments (UEs) without compromising data privacy, a feature particularly advantageous in those applications where data sensitivity and privacy are of key importance. The application of FL is thus becoming relevant in many applications, spanning from healthcare to autonomous driving [5].

However, the reliability of wireless communications, fundamental for the efficient transmission of model updates in FL, is challenged by the inherent instability of wireless channels [6]. Adopting Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) is a common approach for dealing with the unpredictability of wireless communication, as it enhances transmission reliability. However, this reliability comes at the cost of increased communication overhead, often requiring multiple transmissions of the

same message. On the other hand, User Datagram Protocol (UDP) does not guarantee the delivery of each packet but can outperform TCP in communication efficiency. Despite its efficiency, UDP unreliability poses challenges for FL systems, where accurate and complete model updates are essential for quick model convergence. Network coding can provide an effective alternative in enhancing reliable packet transmission in dynamic 6G networks [7].

This work addresses these challenges by integrating Fountain Codes (FC), a class of robust network codes originally designed for multimedia streaming [8], into the FL process. FC offers a significant reduction in packet transmission requirements, outperforming traditional TCP in environments characterized by packet loss. By employing a cumulative acknowledgment strategy tailored for FL, this demonstration shows how improvements of model update transmissions can be obtained in dynamic 6G networks, with a converged Radio Access Network (RAN)-Core Network (CN) architecture [9].

II. INNOVATION AND RELEVANCE

The implementation proposed in this demo represents an innovative approach in tackling the problem of unreliable wireless communications for FL. Indeed, practical wireless challenges, such as transmission errors and resource constraints, impact the efficacy of FL [10]. Hence, although many recent works have tailored FL solutions for wireless scenarios [11], there is a lack of studies on how the packet losses and TCP retransmission impacts the FL process.

The in-order arrival of packets required by the error control mechanism of traditional TCP solution can become a burden in the communication process, leading to large retransmission redundancy and longer end-to-end delay, especially in environments characterized by high loss, such as wireless networks [12]. Hence, there is a need to rethink the communication protocol for the efficient transmission of FL model updates in the context of NextG wireless environments.

In this demonstration we present an FC-based cumulative ACK strategy as an alternative to TCP specifically tailored for FL model updates. Indeed it is commonly acknowledged by both industry and academia that every aspect of the NextG wireless networks should be tailored for specific requirements,

including transport layer protocols [13]. Hence, the approach proposed in this paper paves the way for a transport layer protocol specifically tailored for a specific application, i.e., FL, demonstrating how it can outperform traditional TCP solutions under certain network conditions, i.e., high packet loss.

III. DEMO SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND WORKFLOW

Fig. 1 depicts the proposed demo architecture. Regarding the demo scenario of the FL system, motivated by the convergence of RAN and CN as discussed in [9], we implement the PS within the gNB. Both the gNB and the UEs utilize a FC-based communication, operating over UDP connections, for the transmission of FL process parameters.

As highlighted in Fig. 1, the demonstration covers the following steps:

- **Step 1: Model Transmission.** The global model, residing in the gNB, is sent to all participating UEs through FC-based communication. The cumulative ACK strategy ensures that the model is reliably delivered across the network to each UE for the subsequent training step.
- **Step 2: Local Model Training.** Upon receiving the global model, each UE, denoted as UE 1 through UE N in Fig. 1, begins training this model with their own local datasets. The output of this step is a set of local models that have been individually adapted by each UE to better predict outcomes based on the data they have been exposed to.
- **Step 3: Model Aggregation.** After the local models have been trained, they are sent back to the gNB. The transmission back also exploits FC-based communication to ensure a reliable delivery of the updated models. Once all the local models have been collected, the PS performs an aggregation operation exploiting FedAvg, resulting into a single, improved global model. The iteration concludes with an updated global model that incorporates insights from across the network, ready to be transmitted again for further refinement in the next iteration.

These steps are cyclically repeated, allowing the global model to incrementally improve with each iteration. The repetitive nature of this process facilitates continuous learning and model refinement. Throughout this iterative process, the quantity of packets exchanged and the time needed to complete a model update exchange via both traditional TCP connection and the proposed FC method are recorded. These data are displayed on a real-time chart, providing immediate visualization and analysis of the communication efficiency and overhead associated with each method. The number of packets sent by both gNB and UE over several rounds is reported in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively.

Results demonstrate that the average number of packets sent using the FC-based FL system consistently remains below that of the TCP-based methods for both gNB and UEs, observing an average reduction in the packet count transmitted by the gNB and the UEs by 21% and 20%, respectively.

IV. TECHNICAL ASPECTS

The demonstration of the FL system relies on the Saint Louis University testbed, which includes the gNB, implemented using the OpenAirInterface (OAI) software, a versatile and open-source platform that enables the simulation, development, and testing of 5G radio access network technologies. This choice ensures that the gNB is not only standards-compliant but also flexible for research and development purposes. For the radio hardware, we employ the USRP X310, a powerful and highly flexible software-defined radio platform capable of handling the high throughput and processing demands of FL applications.

The UEs participating in the FL process represent a heterogeneous network environment. A part of the UEs is based on the OpenAirInterface software stack. Additionally, this setup includes Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) UEs to validate the proposed FL system with real-world equipment. The COTS UEs provide an essential benchmark for understanding how the FL system performs on widely available hardware.

The FC algorithm exploited is RaptorQ, a class of rateless codes characterized for their linear time encoding and decoding complexity, robustness in packet loss scenarios, and ability to generate a potentially limitless number of encoding symbols from a given set of original symbols. These characteristics make them highly efficient for data transmission over unreliable networks [14].

Concerning the communication, a cumulative ACK strategy based on FC is used to ensure the successful transmission of data packets over a network. The receiver keeps decoding incoming packets until it manages to successfully reconstruct the original inputs. If the original packet is reconstructed, then the receiver sends an ACK message to the sender. On the sender side, packets are transmitted in a continuous manner until a "STOP" ACK is received, indicating successful receipt; if no ACK is received within a short period, then the sender keeps transmitting packets.

V. CONCLUSION

This demo showed a cumulative ACK strategy based on FC, representing an alternative to classical TCP communications. The proposed algorithm consistently outperforms TCP-based methods in terms of number of sent packets for both gNB and UEs, paving the way for future transport layer protocols specifically tailored for FL scenarios.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is partly supported by the project CLEVER (project number 101097560). The project is supported by the Key Digital Technologies Joint Undertaking and its members (including top-up funding by the Italian Ministry of Research and University (MUR)). This work is also partially supported by the European Union under the Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) of NextGenerationEU, partnership on "Telecommunications of the Future" (PE00000001 - program "RESTART"), by the project Smart Computing and

Fig. 1. Proposed demo architecture, where next generation eNB (gNB) acts the Parameter Server (PS) of the FL process.

Fig. 2. Packet sends per round: gNB side.

Fig. 3. Packet sends per round: UE side.

Communication at the Edge (SMARTCOM) funded by SMARTy and CNR, and by the Italian MUR in the framework of the FoReLab project (Departments of Excellence).

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